

GEOGRAPHICAL BASES OF USE OF NATURAL RESOURCE POTENTIAL OF KASHKADARYA REGION.

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Normatova Gulasal Berdiyori qizi

Tashkent State Pedagogical University

1st year student of master's degree

Abstract: *Through this article, we are going to explore main geographical bases of use of natural resource potential of Kashkadarya region. Additionally, facts about the specific features of region were given.*

Key Words: *arid zone, bio-geographical, vascular, gold deposits, copper, gold, natural gas, cotton, agricultural activities.*

Uzbekistan is situated in the arid zone, which includes large natural sources of dust from the Kara-Kum and Kyzyl-Kum deserts with their repeated windstorms, the Aral Sea area zone (Priaralye) and the dried Aral seabed area (Aralkum). Soil and mineral particles are the main constituents of suspended particulate matters from these sources. In Uzbekistan, sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and carbon monoxide (CO), and suspended particulates of different composition and origin are the main anthropogenic air pollutants. Uzbekistan is located at the crossroads of several bio-geographical regions. It contains a variety of landscapes, including high mountain ranges, wetlands, and the infamous Aral Sea. Almost 85 % of Uzbekistan's territory is occupied by desert or semi desert, including the largest arid zones in Central Asia: the Kyzyl-Kum, and the Ustyurt Plateau. About 10 % of Uzbekistan's land, most of it in the Fergana Valley, is classified as arable, and 0.8 % is planted to permanent agricultural crops. About 0.4% is forested. Most of the rest is desert. The flora of Uzbekistan is represented by at least 4,800 species of vascular plants which belong to 650 genera and 115 families. Endemism rate is rather low at 8 % or 400 species of the total number of species. Economic production is concentrated in commodities.

Uzbekistan has the fourth largest gold deposits in the world. The country mines 80 tons of gold annually, seventh in the world. Uzbekistan's copper deposits rank tenth in the world and its uranium deposits twelfth. The country's uranium production ranks seventh globally. The Uzbek national gas company, Uzbekneftegas, ranks 11th in the world in natural gas production with an annual output of 60 to 70 billion cubic metres (2.1–2.5

trillion cubic feet). The country has significant untapped reserves of oil and gas: there are 194 deposits of hydrocarbons in Uzbekistan, including 98 condensate and natural gas deposits and 96 gas condensate deposits. Along with many Commonwealth of Independent States or CIS economies, Uzbekistan's economy declined during the first years of transition and then recovered after 1995, as the cumulative effect of policy reforms began to be felt. Since the mid-2000s, Uzbekistan has enjoyed robust GDP growth due to the trade of its key export commodities like copper, gold, natural gas, and cotton, and coupled with the government's macro-economic management and limited exposure to international financial markets that protected it from the economic downturn. Overall GDP growth for Uzbekistan has continued at around 8 % annually during 2011-15, supported by net exports and a large capital investment program. Agriculture employs 26% of Uzbekistan's labour force and contributes 18% of its GDP (2012 data). Cultivable land is 4.4 million hectares, or about 10% of Uzbekistan's total area.

The Kashkadarya region has significant petroleum and natural gas reserves, with the Mubarekh Oil and Gas Processing Plant as the region's largest industry. Other industry includes wool processing, textiles, light industry, food processing and construction materials. Major agricultural activities include cotton, various crops and livestock. The irrigation infrastructure is very well developed with the large Tollimarjon reservoir providing reliable water source. The economy of the Kashkadarya Region and the Project area is focused on agriculture. The share of agricultural production in Kashkadarya in the gross regional product is more than 40%. The gross agricultural output of the region is 796.1 billion soms. Kashkadarya is one of the main sources of grain, cotton and other agricultural products in Uzbekistan producing 10.2% of all agricultural products (10% of cotton, 11% of grain). 98% of gas and more than 80% of oil extracted in Uzbekistan comes from Kashkadarya. [Natural resources](#) include significant [petroleum](#) and [natural gas](#) reserves, with the [Muborak](#) Oil and Gas Processing Plant as the region's largest industry. Other industry includes [wool](#) processing, [textiles](#), [light industry](#), [food processing](#) and [construction](#) materials. Major agricultural activities include [cotton](#), various crops and [livestock](#).

The [irrigation](#) infrastructure is very well developed with the large [Tallimarjon](#) Reservoir as a reliable water source. The region has a well-developed transport infrastructure, with over 350 km of railways and 4000 km of surfaced roads. The public procurement shall be implemented in the

form of the competitive bidding in the event of the simultaneous occurrence of the following conditions:

- it is possible to formulate a detailed and accurate description of goods (works, services);
- criteria for selecting the winner have not only a monetary value, but also a quantitative and qualitative evaluation of the goods (works, services);

- cost of goods shall be in the range from five thousand times the minimum wage up to twenty five thousand times the minimum wage per contract; cost of works, services shall be in the range from twenty five times the minimum wage up to twenty five thousand times the minimum wage per contract. In order for the public procurement through competitive bidding to happen, the following conditions must be met:

- cost of goods shall be in the range from two thousand five hundred times the minimum wage up to six thousand times the minimum wage per contract;

- cost of works, services shall be in the range from twenty five times the minimum wage up to six thousand times the minimum wage per contract. To improve access of the private companies to public procurement tenders, the Government enacted a rule according to which state-owned natural monopoly entities, state unitary enterprises and majority-owned companies by state (owning more than 50%) have to announce their procurement tenders for goods (works, services) via electronic trades on the Uzbek Republican Commodity Exchange. The Law "On public procurement" stipulates the following quantitative thresholds for difference means of procurement:

- If the amount of purchase of a good or service is 6,000 BCU or above, the public organization must use tenders to make a purchase. When the public procurement of goods (works, services) is carried out using funds of the State budget, a tender commission should be formed. Such tenders can be carried out by ministries, agencies, khokimiyats, schools, state preschool educational institutions and other organizations financed from the budget. Natural monopoly entities, state unitary enterprises and companies with state share in charter capitals of more than 50% are also subject to this legislation. According to the Law "On public procurement", an announcement about the public procurement tenders must be placed on a special electronic procurement portal for at least 10 days to solicit all proposals.

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